

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF COUNSELING NEEDS AMONG URBAN AND RURAL SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE POST-COVID-19 PERIOD (JULY 2022 – JUNE 2024): IMPLICATIONS FOR SCHOOL COUNSELING SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a comparative analysis of counseling needs among secondary school students from urban and rural areas in Malaysia during the post-COVID-19 period (July 2022–June 2024). A total of 400 students were selected through cluster sampling from four schools, two urban and two rural. The investigation employed the Secondary School Students' Counseling Needs Assessment to identify gaps across six domains: personal development, academic performance, emotional well-being, career planning, peer interaction, and family-related concerns. Paired samples t-tests revealed statistically significant differences ($p < 0.001$) and notable discrepancies between students' desired and current counseling experiences across all six domains in both urban and rural settings, confirming the presence of unmet counseling needs. The analysis also identified differences in the prioritization of needs between the two groups. Urban students reported the greatest gaps in personal development (1.20), academics (1.14), and emotional needs (1.07), while rural students prioritized academic needs (1.13), personal development (1.09), and emotional well-being (0.75). These findings highlight the importance of geographically responsive counseling interventions that reflect the distinct developmental challenges and contextual realities of students from diverse school environments.

Keywords: counseling needs, post-COVID-19, secondary school students, school counseling services, counseling needs priorities

INTRODUCTION

School counseling services are vital components of the education system, offering critical support for students' academic progress, emotional balance, and social maturity. Secondary school students, in particular, navigate a complex developmental period characterized by identity exploration, growing autonomy, and increased vulnerability to academic and interpersonal stress (Ruiz & Yabut, 2024). The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted these formative experiences, amplifying emotional distress and social detachment during a time when psychological stability is essential (Singh et al., 2020). As a result, the need for counseling interventions tailored to adolescents' developmental and contextual realities has become more pressing than ever.

This research adopts Maslow's hierarchy of needs as its conceptual foundation, a model that emphasizes the sequential fulfillment of human needs, starting with physiological and safety concerns, and progressing toward psychological growth and self-actualization (Maslow, 1954). In the realm of secondary education, this framework suggests that optimal learning and personal advancement are unlikely unless students' basic emotional and social needs are adequately supported, an issue made more urgent in the wake of the pandemic's disruption.

A growing body of empirical studies affirms the vital role of school counseling in helping adolescents navigate academic stressors and psychological challenges. Mahyatun (2023), Rock (2023), and Warren et al. (2024) have all demonstrated the positive impact of counseling services on managing issues such as anxiety, peer conflict, and emotional well-being. The professional and ethical responsibility of school counselors includes delivering holistic services that adapt to the shifting needs of student populations (Erford, 2011). Central to this mission is the use of needs assessment tools that help counselors collect relevant data, pinpoint areas of concern, and make informed decisions about resource allocation (Schmidt, 2013). The Malaysian Ministry of Education similarly advocates for data-driven, student-centered approaches in crafting school-based counseling interventions (Kementerian Pendidikan Malaysia, 2015).

Malaysia provides a meaningful context for this inquiry, given the marked disparities in educational access and support services between its urban and rural regions. Students in urban centers often contend with competitive academic environments and heightened safety concerns (Lee, 2005), while their rural counterparts face constraints in both infrastructure and access to trained mental health professionals (Fears et al., 2023). Despite these realities, existing research tends to generalize findings or treat these settings in isolation. Moreover, limited attention has been given to how student counseling needs have shifted in the aftermath of COVID-19, particularly from a comparative, geographically sensitive perspective.

In response, this study aims to bridge that gap by examining how counseling needs vary between urban and rural secondary school students during the post-COVID-19 period. The goal is to uncover both common and context-specific needs that can inform more targeted and equitable counseling practices. Ultimately, the study's findings are intended to assist school counselors, administrators, and policymakers in designing responsive strategies that foster student well-being across Malaysia's educational landscape.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of "needs" is both foundational and complex, particularly when viewed through the lens of human development and educational planning. Needs are shaped by a range of individual and contextual factors, such as socio-economic background, cultural orientation, and environmental influences. Foundational scholars like Kaufman and English (1976), Gupta et al. (2014), and Watkins et al. (2012) conceptualize needs as the measurable gap between an existing state ("what is") and a desired outcome ("what should be"). Known as the "gap model," this approach serves as a practical framework for prioritizing interventions, especially in the educational sector, where aligning support services with actual student needs is critical for strategic resource deployment.

A major advantage of the gap model is its adaptability to real-world decision-making. By quantifying the discrepancy between current and ideal conditions it offers a structured means for identifying where interventions are most needed. Gap analysis, as a core element of this model, plays a pivotal role in needs assessments. Guyette (1983) noted that positive gap scores often highlight areas where proactive strategies can make a meaningful impact, while negative gaps may signal inefficiencies or misalignments in current service delivery that warrant re-evaluation.

Within the field of school counseling, needs assessment serves as a crucial mechanism for developing student-centered and contextually relevant interventions. Several recent studies underscore the relevance of the gap model in varied educational settings. Dharmi and Sharma (2020), for instance, explored counseling needs among adolescents in both rural and urban areas of Punjab, India, concluding that rural students exhibited greater psychological need. Their findings illustrate how geographical and societal conditions, such as service accessibility and cultural perceptions of mental health, directly influence the types of support students require.

Likewise, Rosvall (2020) examined career guidance disparities among rural students in Sweden and observed a recurring pattern of decisions shaped by a "learning to leave" mentality. This phenomenon highlights how structural inequities, such as reduced access to qualified counselors or information, can constrain students' aspirations and limit their perceived opportunities.

Such studies reaffirm the versatility of the gap model in identifying context-specific counseling needs across different educational landscapes. Far from being rigid, the model is flexible enough to reflect the nuanced experiences of students when applied with cultural and contextual awareness. Its strength lies in its ability to adapt across settings while still yielding actionable insights.

Beyond identifying gaps, effective needs assessments can shape broader institutional decisions from curriculum design to service delivery strategies. When combined with cultural sensitivity, they become powerful tools for transformative change in school counseling. The integration of empirical data, such as gap scores, with students' lived experiences allows stakeholders to design interventions that are not only evidence-based but also empathetic and tailored to real-world student needs.

In sum, needs assessment, grounded in the foundational work of Kaufman, Gupta, Watkins, and others, remains a cornerstone of effective educational planning. Its application in school counseling helps ensure that services are not only evidence-based but also responsive to the evolving and diverse needs of students, particularly in post-pandemic contexts. Through thoughtful application of gap analysis and contextual awareness, educators and counselors can build systems that truly support students' holistic development.

METHOD

The study employed a quantitative, cross-sectional survey design to examine the counseling needs of secondary school students across urban and rural contexts. This approach allowed the researchers to gather data at a specific point in time, offering a snapshot of students' perceived and actual counseling requirements. The methodology was selected to align with the study's aim of comparing variable patterns between different populations and testing predetermined hypotheses. Specifically, the study tested the following:

- i. H1: There are significant differences between students' desired counseling needs ("what should be") and their current experiences ("what is") in both urban and rural school settings.
- ii. H2: The prioritization of counseling needs varies significantly between urban and rural respondents.

SITE, SAMPLE AND SAMPLING PROCEDURE

Data were collected from four public secondary schools in Malaysia, two situated in urban locations and two in rural districts. The sample size was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) formula, based on a national secondary school enrollment figure of 1,984,995 students as of January 2022 (Department of Statistics Malaysia, 2024). A total sample of 400 students was deemed representative for this study.

Schools were selected through a multi-level cluster random sampling process to ensure diversity and reduce bias. The urban sample comprised two schools from the Klang Valley, a densely populated metropolitan region with access to robust educational and counseling infrastructure. The rural sample was drawn from two schools in Kemaman, Terengganu, a district characterized by more limited access to such services. This geographical selection allowed for meaningful comparisons between contrasting contexts without aiming for full national generalizability.

Within each selected school, 100 students aged 13 to 17 years were randomly chosen, with attention to gender balance. Using entire schools as sampling clusters streamlined the data collection while preserving randomization integrity.

INSTRUMENT

The primary data collection tool was the Secondary School Students' Counseling Needs Assessment Instrument, developed and validated by Jailani (2021). This instrument is divided into two sections: Section A gathers demographic information (e.g., age, gender, ethnicity), while Section B measures counseling needs across six domains: personal development (6 items), academic (4 items), family (5 items), emotional (3 items), peer relationships (3 items), and career development (4 items).

A dual-response format was used in Section B to capture students' ideal expectations (Column A: "what should be") and their current lived experiences (Column B: "what is"). Responses were recorded on a six-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 6 (Strongly Agree), intentionally omitting a neutral midpoint to encourage more decisive responses, an important strategy in identifying actual gaps in perceived needs.

Reliability testing during a pilot involving 40 students produced high Cronbach's alpha values: 0.96 for desired needs and 0.94 for current needs. Content validity was established through expert panel review, while exploratory analysis in prior studies confirmed the instrument's construct validity (Jailani, 2021).

DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURES

Both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were employed to analyze the data, using SPSS Version 26 as the primary tool for processing. To address the first hypothesis (H1), the study utilized a paired samples t-test to assess differences between students' perceived ideal counseling needs (Column A) and their reported current experiences (Column B) across six need domains. Mean (*M*) scores were calculated for each domain, and the gap score was derived using the formula:

$$\text{Gap} = \text{Desired (Column A)} - \text{Current (Column B)}$$

Positive gap values indicated areas of unmet need, reflecting domains where students desire more support than they currently receive, a concept aligned with Guyette's (1983) interpretation of gaps as markers for intervention. Negative values, if present, could suggest over-provision or misalignment of services.

To test the second hypothesis (H2), which posits that the magnitude of counseling needs differs across urban and rural settings, the Mean scores were further examined alongside their Standard Deviations (*SD*). A standardized gap ratio was calculated for each domain by dividing the Mean by the Standard Deviation (M/SD). According to Samuels (2014), an M/SD value nearing 2.0 signals a substantial gap and therefore higher priority for intervention. This approach enabled clearer comparisons across counseling domains and allowed for the ranking of needs based on severity.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The study was conducted in full accordance with established ethical research protocols, prioritizing the rights, dignity, and well-being of all student participants. Informed consent was obtained prior to data collection, with students made fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any stage without penalty. Participation was entirely voluntary.

To promote fairness and inclusivity, the sample included students from both urban and rural schools, representing a range of genders and backgrounds. No personal identifiers were collected, ensuring participant anonymity and data confidentiality. All information gathered was used solely for academic purposes and stored securely, accessible only to the research team. These ethical safeguards were designed to uphold integrity and protect participants throughout the research process.

RESULTS

The data were collected from two urban and two rural schools, with 400 students participating in the survey by answering the questionnaires. The demographic backgrounds of the respondents are detailed in Tables 1 and 2. In urban schools, the demographic profile reveals a higher proportion of females, comprising 61.5% of the 200 respondents, compared to 38.5% of males. The respondents' ages range from 13 to 17 years, with 13-year-olds accounting for 0.5%, 14-year-olds 4.5%, 15-year-olds 40.5%, 16-year-olds 20.0%, and 17-year-olds 34.5%. In terms of racial diversity, Malay students form the majority at 86%, followed by Indian students at 11%, and Chinese students at 3%. In rural schools, the gender distribution is similar, with females representing 60.5% and males 39.5% of the 200 respondents. The age range is also between 13 and 17 years, with 13-year-olds comprising 20.5%, 14-year-olds 31.5%, 15-year-olds 10.5%, 16-year-olds 21.0%, and 17-year-olds 16.5%. Unlike urban schools, rural schools show no racial diversity, as all 200 respondents identify as Malay.

Table 1. Demographic information of respondents from urban schools

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS n = 200	VALID PERCENTAGE (%)
Gender		
Male	77	38.5
Female	123	61.5
Age		
13-year-old	1	0.5
14-year-old	9	4.5
15-year-old	81	40.5
16-year-old	40	20.0
17-year-old	69	34.5
Race		
Malay	172	86.0
Chinese	6	3.0
Indian	22	11.0

Table 2. Demographic information of respondents from rural schools

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS n = 200	VALID PERCENTAGE (%)
Gender		
Male	79	39.5
Female	121	60.5
Age		
13-year-old	41	20.5
14-year-old	63	31.5
15-year-old	21	10.5
16-year-old	42	21.0
17-year-old	33	16.5
Race		
Malay	200	100.0
Chinese	0	0
Indian	0	0

Before the study, the data were thoroughly checked for accuracy in data entry, as well as any missing values, skewness, and kurtosis coefficients. All items were entered correctly, and the skewness and kurtosis coefficients showed stability. After this initial check, the data from urban and rural schools were analyzed using the paired samples t-test.

The results of the paired samples t-test revealed significant differences between the desired needs (Column A) and current needs (Column B) of urban school respondents across six counseling needs domains or components. For personal development needs, the mean scores were $M = 5.41$ ($SD = 0.53$) for Column A and $M = 4.47$ ($SD = 0.84$) for Column B; $t(199) = 16.96$, $p < 0.001$. Similarly, academic needs showed mean scores of $M = 5.45$ ($SD = 0.60$) for Column A and $M = 4.48$ ($SD = 0.88$) for Column B; $t(199) = 16.12$, $p < 0.001$. For family needs, the mean scores were $M = 5.48$ ($SD = 0.62$) for Column A and $M = 4.98$ ($SD = 0.85$) for Column B; $t(199) = 9.03$, $p < 0.001$. Emotional needs showed mean scores of $M = 5.37$ ($SD = 0.75$) for Column A and $M = 4.32$ ($SD = 1.03$) for Column B; $t(199) = 15.13$, $p < 0.001$. Peer relationship needs revealed mean scores of $M = 5.43$ ($SD = 0.66$) for Column A and $M = 4.88$ ($SD = 0.80$) for Column B; $t(199) = 10.27$, $p < 0.001$. Finally, for career development needs, the mean scores were $M = 5.60$ ($SD = 0.56$) for Column A and $M = 4.96$ ($SD = 0.84$) for Column B; $t(199) = 12.41$, $p < 0.001$. Detailed findings are presented in Tables 3 and 4. To illustrate the differences between Column A and Column B, Table 5 presents the discrepancies in values, with all scores represented as positive figures.

Table 3. Discrepancies of Mean (M) and Standard Deviation (SD) of respondents from urban schools

COUNSELING NEEDS COMPONENTS	DESIRED/CURRENT NEEDS	MEAN (M)	n	STD. DEVIATION (SD)	STD. ERROR MEAN
Personal development needs	Column A	5.41	200	0.53	0.04
	Column B	4.47		0.84	0.06
Academic needs	Column A	5.45	200	0.60	0.04
	Column B	4.48		0.88	0.06
Family needs	Column A	5.48	200	0.62	0.04
	Column B	4.98		0.85	0.06
Emotional needs	Column A	5.37	200	0.75	0.05
	Column B	4.32		1.03	0.07
Peer relationship needs	Column A	5.43	200	0.66	0.05
	Column B	4.88		0.80	0.06
Career development needs	Column A	5.60	200	0.56	0.04
	Column B	4.96		0.84	0.06

Table 4. The Paired Samples t-test of respondents from urban schools

COUNSELING NEEDS COMPONENTS	MEAN (M)	STD. DEVIATION (SD)	STD. ERROR	LOWER	UPPER	t	DF	SIG. (2-TAILED)
Personal development needs	0.93	0.78	0.06	0.83	1.042	16.96	199	0.001
Academic needs	0.97	0.85	0.06	0.85	1.09	16.12	199	0.001
Family needs	0.50	0.78	0.06	0.39	0.61	9.03	199	0.001
Emotional needs	1.05	0.98	0.07	0.92	1.19	15.13	199	0.001
Peer relationship needs	0.56	0.76	0.05	0.45	0.66	10.27	199	0.001
Career development needs	0.64	0.73	0.05	0.54	0.74	12.41	199	0.001

Table 5: Discrepancy values of Column A and Column B of urban school students

COUNSELING NEEDS COMPONENTS	COLUMN A	COLUMN B	DISCREPANCIES
Personal development needs	5.41	4.47	0.94
Academic needs	5.45	4.48	0.97
Family needs	5.48	4.98	0.50
Emotional needs	5.37	4.32	1.05
Peer relationship needs	5.43	4.88	0.55
Career development needs	5.60	4.96	0.64

The results presented in Tables 6 and 7 indicate significant differences between the desired needs (Column A) and current needs (Column B) across all counseling needs components as reported by rural school respondents. For personal development needs, the mean scores were $M = 5.27$ ($SD = 0.51$) for Column A and $M = 4.58$ ($SD = 0.73$) for Column B; $t(199) = 15.36$, $p < 0.001$. In the case of academic needs, the mean scores were $M = 5.24$ ($SD = 0.59$) for Column A and $M = 4.55$ ($SD = 0.73$) for Column B; $t(199) = 16.05$, $p < 0.001$. For family needs, the mean scores were $M = 5.37$ ($SD = 0.54$) for Column A and $M = 5.16$ ($SD = 0.75$) for Column B; $t(199) = 5.68$, $p < 0.001$. Emotional needs showed mean scores of $M = 5.29$ ($SD = 0.61$) for Column A and $M = 4.67$ ($SD = 0.84$) for Column B; $t(199) = 10.66$, $p < 0.001$. Peer relationship needs demonstrated mean scores of $M = 5.33$ ($SD = 0.66$) for Column A and $M = 5.00$ ($SD = 0.76$) for Column B; $t(199) = 7.10$, $p < 0.001$. Lastly, for career development needs, the mean scores were $M = 5.47$ ($SD = 0.56$) for Column A and $M = 5.13$ ($SD = 0.69$) for Column B; $t(199) = 7.30$, $p < 0.001$. Table 8 highlights the discrepancy values between Column A and Column B, with all figures presented as positive values.

Table 6. Discrepancies of Mean (M) and Standard Deviation (SD) of respondents from rural schools

COUNSELING NEEDS COMPONENTS	DESIRED/CURRENT NEEDS	MEAN (M)	n	STD. DEVIATION (SD)	STD. ERROR MEAN
Personal development needs	Column A	5.27	200	0.51	0.04
	Column B	4.58		0.73	0.05
Academic needs	Column A	5.24	200	0.59	0.04
	Column B	4.55		0.73	0.05
Family needs	Column A	5.37	200	0.54	0.05
	Column B	5.16		0.75	0.05
Emotional needs	Column A	5.29	200	0.61	0.04
	Column B	4.67		0.84	0.06
Peer relationship needs	Column A	5.33	200	0.66	0.05
	Column B	5.00		0.76	0.05
Career development needs	Column A	5.47	200	0.56	0.04
	Column B	5.13		0.69	0.05

Table 7. The Paired Samples t-test of respondents from rural schools

COUNSELING NEEDS COMPONENTS	MEAN (M)	STD. DEVIATION (SD)	STD. ERROR	LOWER	UPPER	t	DF	SIG. (2-TAILED)
Personal development needs	0.69	0.64	0.04	0.60	0.78	15.36	199	0.001
Academic needs	0.69	0.61	0.04	0.60	0.77	16.05	199	0.001
Family needs	0.21	0.52	0.04	0.14	0.28	5.68	199	0.001
Emotional needs	0.62	0.82	0.06	0.51	0.74	10.66	199	0.001
Peer relationship needs	0.33	0.65	0.05	0.24	0.42	7.10	199	0.001
Career development needs	0.34	0.65	0.05	0.25	0.43	7.30	199	0.001

Table 8. Discrepancy values of Column A and Column B of rural school students

COUNSELING NEEDS COMPONENTS	COLUMN A	COLUMN B	DISCREPANCIES
Personal development needs	5.27	4.58	0.69
Academic needs	5.24	4.55	0.69
Family needs	5.37	5.16	0.21
Emotional needs	5.29	4.67	0.62
Peer relationship needs	5.33	5.00	0.33
Career development needs	5.47	5.13	0.34

The paired samples t-test results for urban and rural respondents, along with the discrepancy values as illustrated above, support the first hypothesis (H1) of this study: There are significant differences between students' desired counseling needs ("what should be") and their current experiences ("what is") in both urban and rural school settings. These differences were measured across six components of counseling needs using the research instrument. The findings align with Guyette's (1983) assertion that a positive gap score indicates a need for action or intervention, thereby underscoring the importance of school counselors in addressing the unmet needs of students in both urban and rural settings.

To quantify the magnitude of each counseling needs component among urban and rural school respondents, and to test the second hypothesis (H2), which states that 'the prioritization of counseling needs varies significantly between urban and rural respondents,' the Mean (*M*) score for each component was divided by its Standard Deviation (*SD*). Tables 9 and 10 provide detailed gap size scores and priorities for urban and rural respondents.

Table 9. Gap size scores and priorities of respondents from urban schools

COUNSELING COMPONENTS	NEEDS	MEAN (M)	STD. DEVIATION (SD)	GAP SIZE
Personal needs	development	0.93	0.78	1.19
Academic needs		0.97	0.85	1.14
Emotional needs		1.05	0.98	1.07
Career development needs		0.64	0.73	0.88
Peer relationship needs		0.56	0.76	0.73
Family needs		0.50	0.78	0.64

Table 10. Gap size scores and priorities of respondents from rural schools

COUNSELING COMPONENTS	NEEDS	MEAN (M)	STD. DEVIATION (SD)	GAP SIZE
Academic needs		0.69	0.61	1.13
Personal needs	development	0.69	0.64	1.08
Emotional needs		0.62	0.82	0.76
Career development needs		0.34	0.65	0.52
Peer relationship needs		0.33	0.65	0.51
Family needs		0.21	0.52	0.40

Based on the gap size scores, the counseling needs of urban school students are prioritized as follows: personal development (1.19), academic needs (1.14), emotional needs (1.07), career development needs (0.88), peer relationship needs (0.73), and family needs (0.64). In contrast, rural school students ranked their counseling needs in the following order: academic needs (1.13), personal development (1.08), emotional needs (0.76), career development (0.52), peer relationships (0.51), and family needs (0.40). These findings indicate slight differences in the prioritization of counseling needs between urban and rural students. While urban students placed personal development as their highest priority, rural students identified academic needs as most important. Thus, the second hypothesis (H2) is supported.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study offer important contributions to the understanding of how geographical context shapes the counseling needs of Malaysian secondary school students. The pronounced gaps reported by urban students in personal development and emotional well-being suggest that competitive academic settings and fast-paced urban environments may heighten stress and diminish opportunities for self-reflection and emotional resilience, an interpretation that echoes Lee's (2005) analysis of urban schooling. Conversely, the priorities expressed by rural students support earlier findings by Dhami and Sharma (2020), who identified limited access to mental health services and support infrastructure in rural areas as key challenges. Additionally, this study highlights how post-pandemic digital inequities and social isolation may further compound these existing disparities.

Specifically, urban respondents ranked personal development (1.19), academic performance (1.14), and emotional well-being (1.07) as their top counseling priorities, suggesting that the pressures of urban academic culture may overshadow access to internal coping resources (Fears et al., 2023). In comparison, rural students placed the highest emphasis on academic support (1.13), followed closely by personal development (1.08). These preferences likely stem from ongoing disparities in access to academic enrichment, counseling guidance, and career preparation opportunities in rural school environments (Rosvall, 2020). These findings also align closely with Maslow's hierarchy of needs, particularly in illustrating that many students, regardless of location, are still striving to meet intermediate-level needs such as emotional security, academic confidence, and self-esteem. Without these foundational supports, the pursuit of self-actualization through academic and personal achievement becomes difficult. The gap scores across both groups reflect this developmental plateau, reinforcing the argument that school counseling must first address these core needs before higher-level growth can occur.

The contrast in needs profiles across urban and rural settings underscores the importance of differentiated counseling strategies. For urban students, interventions that cultivate emotional regulation, manage academic stress, and build personal identity may be most impactful. In rural schools, however, the focus should center on improving academic scaffolding, expanding developmental opportunities, and strengthening career pathways. Tailoring services in this manner enhances not only short-term support but also students' long-term capacity for self-actualization, consistent with Maslow's theoretical model.

Despite the study's valuable contributions, certain limitations must be acknowledged. First, the sample was restricted to four schools from selected regions, which may not fully capture the diversity of Malaysia's broader secondary school landscape. Second, reliance on self-reported data introduces the possibility of bias, including social desirability effects. Third, the quantitative design, while effective in identifying measurable gaps, does not account for the deeper socio-cultural or psychological underpinnings of these needs.

Future research could expand the geographical scope to include a more diverse range of schools and student populations across Malaysia. Incorporating qualitative components, such as interviews or focus groups, would enrich understanding by capturing student perspectives in greater depth. Longitudinal studies may also help track how students' counseling needs evolve over time, particularly in response to shifting societal conditions or post-pandemic recovery efforts.

In sum, this study reinforces the urgency of context-sensitive, developmentally informed counseling interventions. By grounding these efforts in theoretical models like Maslow's hierarchy and continually refining them through empirical research, school counseling programs can be more responsive, equitable, and impactful in addressing the diverse and dynamic needs of Malaysia's youth.

CONCLUSION

This study underscores the presence of clear disparities in counseling needs between urban and rural secondary school students in Malaysia during the post-COVID-19 period. These differences highlight the significant role that contextual variables, such as location, access to resources, and socio-economic background, play in shaping students' emotional, academic, and developmental priorities. Urban students exhibited greater needs in areas related to personal development, academic stress, and emotional resilience, while rural students placed the highest emphasis on academic support and self-growth.

These findings reaffirm the relevance of Maslow's hierarchy of needs in educational contexts, emphasizing that students require foundational psychological and emotional support before they can realize their full academic and personal potential. Addressing these intermediate needs is essential for fostering conditions conducive to self-actualization.

The implications for practice are clear: school counseling services must be tailored to reflect the specific realities of different educational environments. In urban settings, interventions should prioritize strategies to manage performance pressure and enhance emotional regulation. In rural schools, efforts should focus on strengthening academic scaffolding, improving access to career guidance, and addressing digital and social isolation. These context-sensitive approaches will not only elevate student well-being but also promote greater equity in educational support services nationwide.

To move forward effectively, policymakers and school leaders must prioritize the integration of needs-based, evidence-informed counseling frameworks within Malaysia's education system. Special attention must be given to equipping rural schools with adequate personnel, infrastructure, and resources. Furthermore, continuous professional development for school counselors is essential to ensure they are prepared to meet the evolving and diverse needs of student populations.

In conclusion, this study highlights the importance of adopting differentiated, student-centered approaches to school counseling. Grounded in empirical findings and supported by theoretical insight, such practices are vital for bridging the urban-rural divide and promoting holistic student development across Malaysia's secondary education landscape.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors affirm that there are no conflicts of interest associated with the conduct or publication of this research.

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